

Studies on the Recovery of Phosphate from Basic Slag. I. Application of Hydrated Zirconium Oxide Ion-Exchanger**

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A systematic study of phosphate uptake by hydrated zirconium dioxide has been carried out. The chemical solubility of zirconium dioxide decreases on ageing and the exchanger becomes least soluble after five days of ageing. Ion-exchange capacity, distribution co-efficients of metal ions present in the basic slag and their interference during phosphate uptake have been systematically and critically investigated. Break-through capacity of the exchanger column was determined. A scheme has been proposed for the selective recovery of phosphate from basic slag. Better results were obtained with zirconium dioxide in comparison to tin dioxide.

PANT *et al*¹ observed that basic slag of some Indian Steel Plants contained 0.3 to 7.8% of P_2O_5 . Similar observation was noted in our previous work². Recovery of phosphate from basic slag waste would enhance the available phosphate values. Classical method of phosphate separation from basic slag is time consuming and uneconomical when compared with the ion-exchange method. Boltz³ observed low results of phosphate recovery from large excess of iron(III) using organic cation-exchanger, presumably due to the formation of positively charged iron(III) phosphate complexes which were retained by the ion-exchange resin. Recent development of synthetic inorganic ion-exchanger has tempted us to use inorganic ion-exchanger. In our laboratory, we observed high K_a -value for phosphate using hydrated stannic oxide and this property has been utilised for phosphate recovery in our earlier work². Since Tandon *et al*⁴ and Kraus *et al*⁵ reported high K_a -value for phosphate ($>10^4$) using hydrated zirconium dioxide, our research on phosphate recovery from basic slag now carried out with zirconium dioxide. No such investigation has been carried out before.

This paper reports the systematic studies of phosphate uptake and selective recovery of phosphate from basic slag by zirconium dioxide. Better results were obtained by zirconium dioxide in comparison to stannic oxide.

Experimental

Reagents :

Zirconyloxychloride used is of reagent grade (Indian Rare Earth Ltd.) and all other reagents are of AnalaR grade.

Apparatus :

ELICO pH meter model LI-10 (India) was used

for pH measurement. Spectrophotometer (Electronic Corporation of India Limited), GS 866 B was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

Ion-exchange column (i.d. 1.2. cm, length 3.5 cm) was used for column operation.

Preparation of metal ion and basic slag solution :

Chloride or nitrate salt of metals were dissolved in the corresponding dilute acids (pH 1.5-2.0). Then the required concentration of metal ions were prepared by exact dilution with corresponding dilute acids adjusted to pH 1.5-2.0.

About one gram basic slag was taken accurately and digested with HCl-HNO₃ (25 : 1) mixture in a 400 ml beaker on steam bath upto pasty mass⁶. The digestion procedure was repeated twice. Then the pasty mass dissolved in dilute HCl (pH 1.0-1.5), filtered and was made 250 ml in a volumetric flask.

Preparation of Ion-exchange material :

Hydrated zirconium dioxide was prepared from 0.1M ZrOCl₂ in 0.1M HCl with 0.1M NH₄OH as reported by Tandon *et al*⁴. It was then ignited at 300° in a muffle furnace for one hr before use. Zirconium dioxide of 100-200 mesh was used.

Results and Discussion

Quantitative estimation of different Indian Basic Slags : As reported earlier².

Ion-exchange capacity measurement :

The ion-exchange capacity of hydrated zirconium dioxide (OH⁻ form) was determined by batch

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operation². One gram of hydrated zirconium dioxide was equilibrated with 100 ml of 2.0 M in nitrate ion ($\text{HNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_3$) in 0.1 M HNO_3 for 12 hours. This procedure was repeated with 2.0 M in chloride ion ($\text{HCl} + \text{NaCl}$) in 0.1 M HCl and with sulphate ion ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4$) in 0.1 M H_2SO_4 . The amount of acid neutralized was estimated with standard 0.1 M NaOH . Anion-exchange capacities were given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF HYDRATED ZIRCONIUM DIOXIDE (OH^- -FORM)

Anion solution taken	Initial pH of solution	Final pH of solution	Anion-exchange capacity (meq/gm)
2.0M in chloride ion ($\text{HCl} + \text{NaCl}$) in 0.1M HCl	0.90	1.00	0.965
2.0M in nitrate ion ($\text{HNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_3$) in 0.1M HNO_3	0.90	1.00	0.867
2.0M in sulphate ion ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4$) in 0.1M H_2SO_4	1.75	1.80	1.734

Effect of ageing on solubility in mineral acids :

For determination of solubility, about 500 mg hydrated zirconium dioxide (100-200 mesh) was kept in contact with 100 ml of respective acid solution for 24 hours with intermittent shaking. Then the amount of zirconium dissolved was determined spectrophotometrically by alizarin red-S method⁷. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SOLUBILITY OF HYDRATED ZIRCONIUM DIOXIDE

Solvent taken	Solubility (mg/lit) in 2M solvent	Solubility (mg/lit) in 1M solvent	Solubility (mg/lit) in 0.5M solvent	Solubility (mg/lit) in 0.1M solvent	Solubility (mg/lit) in 0.01M solvent
HCl	52.60	48.40	21.00	2.10	0.00
HNO_3	34.70	32.60	—	7.20	1.2
H_2SO_4	61.00	34.7	—	24.2	6.2

It is interesting to note that the solubility of zirconium dioxide depends on ageing and it decreases with the increase of ageing time (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Effect of ageing on solubility of hydrated zirconium dioxide in mineral acids (1M).

probably due to change in Zr-O lattice structure. The solubility remains almost constant after 5 days of ageing. So throughout our experiment we have used zirconium dioxide after ageing for 5 days. Since zirconium dioxide is insoluble in dilute NaOH solution, it (NaOH) can be better used during phosphate elution from zirconium dioxide.

Distribution co-efficient (K_d) measurement :

The distribution co-efficient (K_d -value) of phosphate, Al(III) , Fe(III) , Ca(II) , Mn(II) and Mg(II) at pH range 1.5-2.0 were determined by equilibrating 100 ml of test solution for 12 hours with one gram of hydrated zirconium dioxide (OH^- -form). The phosphate and metal ion concentrations were kept at $4.2 \times 10^{-4} (M)$ and $4.5 \times 10^{-4} (M)$ respectively. The metal ions and phosphate present in the solution phase before and after shaking were estimated complexometrically⁸ and spectrophotometrically⁸ respectively. The K_d -values were then calculated by the formula

$$K_d = \frac{C_I - C_F}{C_F} \times \frac{100}{\text{Amount of exchanger}}$$

where C_I = Initial concentration and C_F = Final concentration. The K_d -values are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DISTRIBUTION CO-EFFICIENT (K_d) OF THE IONS ON HYDRATED ZIRCONIUM DIOXIDE AT $(22 \pm 2)^\circ$

Anion/Cation	Initial pH	Final pH	K_d -value (ml/gm)
Phosphate	1.60	1.70	Total adsorption
Al(III)	1.90	2.00	4.51
Fe(III)	1.70	1.75	0.71
Mn(II)	1.90	1.95	2.00
Ca(II)	1.70	1.70	1.09
Mg(II)	1.65	1.65	2.83

It should be mentioned here that K_d for Fe(III) with tin dioxide is 32.88 at pH 2 which is much higher than that with zirconium dioxide. Hence it was expected to be easier to remove Fe(III) from phosphate mixture using zirconium dioxide in place of tin dioxide.

Interference study :

The interference due to foreign ions like NO_3^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , Fe(III) , Al(III) , Ca(II) , Mg(II) and Mn(II) during uptake of phosphate by hydrated zirconium dioxide (OH^- -form) in the pH range 1.5-2.0 were studied. 0.5 g of hydrated zirconium dioxide was shaken for 12 hours with 100 ml of solution containing $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ phosphate (fixed) and varying amount of interfering ions. The amount of phosphate present after equilibration was estimated spectrophotometrically by molybdovanadophosphoric method⁸. The amount of phosphate uptake by hydrated zirconium dioxide were calculated by subtraction from the initial amount.

In absence of any foreign ion the uptake of phosphate by 0.5 g hydrated zirconium dioxide was noted to be 37.5 mg. It was observed that initially phosphate uptake decreased to 35 mg due to the presence of 0.1 M Cl^- or NO_3^- ions but phosphate uptake initially decreased to its half value (19.2 mg) in the presence of 0.1 M SO_4^{2-} ion, then gradually upto 2.0 M SO_4^{2-} ion concentration. At 3.0 M SO_4^{2-} ion concentration, phosphate uptake by the hydrated zirconium dioxide was lowered down to 9.6 mg. This was in agreement with the high uptake value for SO_4^{2-} ion [$K_{\text{dSO}_4^{2-}} = 1566$ observed by Tandon⁴].

It clearly indicates that sulphate ions compete with phosphate ions for the exchange sites of the exchanger during equilibrium. Usually phosphate ion is more selective than sulphate ion by hydrated zirconium dioxide exchanger. At high sulphate ion concentration the selectivity is reversed. When the metal : phosphate mole ratio was 1 : 1 or 2 : 1, interference due to Ca(II) , Mg(II) , Mn(II) , Al(III) and Fe(III) ions during phosphate uptake was only slightly. Phosphate uptake by the exchanger due to the presence of 10^{-3} M Ca(II) , Mg(II) , Mn(II) , Al(III) and Fe(III) individually in the solution phase were noted to be 30 mg, 31.5 mg, 34.5 mg and 27 mg respectively. This has consistence with the K_d -value of metal ions. Interference due to Fe(III) and Al(III) became high when the metal : phosphate mole ratio was 20 : 1 due to precipitation.

Column elution study :

Breakthrough capacity (column capacity) of an exchanger for a particular ion is an important parameter for practical column operation. It focus more clear picture than the total exchange capacity of an exchanger. Breakthrough capacity of hydrated zirconium dioxide was determined at pH 1 to 4 as follows : Ion-exchange column (i.d. 1.2 cm, length 3.5 cm) was prepared with 5.0 gm hydrated zirconium dioxide (OH^- -form). The required pH of the exchanger column and of phosphate solution (0.88 mg/ml) were adjusted with dil HCl. The phosphate solutions were then passed through the column with a flow rate 1 ml/min. The concentration of phosphate in the influent and effluent were denoted as C_0 and C respectively. The results were shown in Fig. 2. It was noted that leakage of phosphate was started at pH-1 and 2 after 180 ml and 120 ml of effluent respectively. At pH-3 and 4, the leakage of phosphate was noted after 100 ml of effluent. This has consistence with the fact that anion exchange capacity of zirconium dioxide decreases with the increase of pH. From these results, it is evident that the maximum phosphate was adsorbed quantitatively by zirconium dioxide column under above condition at pH-1, 2 and 3 or 4 are 158.4 mg ; 105.6 mg and 88.0 mg respectively. In this respect zirconium dioxide is much better than tin dioxide (8.8 mg phosphate at pH 2-4)⁵. At pH-1, the major amount of phosphate ion exist as $\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^{9,10}$ and presumably is adsorbed accordingly.

Fig. 2. Breakthrough curves of phosphate (0.88 mg/ml) on hydrated zirconium dioxide (5.0g) column at different pH. Flow rate \approx 1 ml per minute.

During column adsorption and elution studies with individual ion such as Al(III) , Fe(III) , Mn(II) , Ca(II) , Mg(II) and phosphate at pH-2, it was observed that all the metal ions were simply percolated through the exchanger bed and were collected quantitatively in the effluent. Only phosphate was adsorbed strongly by hydrated zirconium dioxide and eluted quantitatively with 100 ml of aqueous 1.0 M NaOH. The rate of elution was kept at 0.5 ml/min. Selective separation of phosphate from the binary mixture of phosphate - Fe(III) , phosphate - Al(III) , phosphate - Mn(II) , phosphate - Ca(II) and phosphate - Mg(II) have been achieved successfully in the pH range 1.5-2.0.

Recovery of phosphate from Basic Slag :

A synthetic mixture of basic slag similar in composition to Burnpur Basic Slag was prepared (pH-1.4). 10 ml aliquot of that solution was added to the top of the exchanger column (OH^- -form). The column was washed with 40 ml of water at pH-1 (adjusted with HCl). The washed solution was first analysed quantitatively for phosphate and found absent, then analysed quantitatively from duplicate runs for all other metal ions. All the metal ions were present quantitatively in the combined effluent and washed solutions. Adsorbed phosphate was then eluted with 100 ml of aqueous 1.0M NaOH and estimated spectrophotometrically⁹.

The above experiment was repeated with the Burnpur Basic Slag, Bokaro Basic Slag and B.A.S. Basic Slag solution. pH of the above basic slag solutions were kept at 1.2-1.5 (adjusted with HCl). The recovery of phosphate was reproducible and highly satisfactory. The results are tabulated in Table 4.

Conclusion :

This procedure can be utilised not only to the recovery of phosphate from solid waste (of price nothing), but also it can help disposal of huge solid waste from Indian Steel Plants.

TABLE 4—RECOVERY OF PHOSPHATE FROM BASIC SLAG

Basic Slag's solution pH 1.2-1.5	Phosphate taken (mg)	Phosphate recove- red by elution (mg)	% of recovery
Synthetic mixture of			
Burnpur basic slag	2.00	1.98	99.00
Burnpur basic slag	2.03	2.00	98.50
*Burnpur basic slag	95.00	90.50	95.20
Bokaro basic slag	2.20	2.18	97.00
B.A.S. (31-a) basic slag	2.82	2.80	99.20
*B.A.S. (31-a) basic slag	99.90	96.40	96.50

* pH of the solution was kept at 1 and the volume containing about 100 mg phosphate was maintained at 250 ml in order to lower the concentration of metal ions in solution. In this case column was washed after passing slag solution with 60 ml of water at pH=0.5 adjusted with dil HCl and phosphate was eluted with 150 ml of aqueous 1.0M NaOH.

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